

Guidelines – Annotation of Syntax and Information Structure in Old Norwegian

The project "Syntactic Variation and Information Structure in Old Norwegian" at the University of Bergen (PhD project, Tiemann) combines annotation and analytic work. The aim of the project is to document, analyze, and explain information-structural phenomena that are responsible for syntactic structuring and variation in the text of *Konungs skuggsjá*, in the Old Norwegian main manuscript AM 243 bǫ fol. The results of this study can be used to extract general pragmatic rules and generalizations about the information structure in Old Norwegian. In order to compare this language with other older languages in international projects, the guidelines presented here follow to a large extent the annotation manuals from two DFG-projects¹ in Germany (see Schnaus & Schneider forthcoming). However, there have been made adaptations to reflect Old Norwegian language traits and incorporating the analyses done within the Menotec-project². Each sentence in the corpus contains annotations on three major levels: 1. glossing, 2. tiers that are relevant for the information-structural analysis, 3. elements of sentence structure. The annotation itself was done in the 1.6. EXMARaLDA Partitur Editor³, while the individual searches within the project were performed in the ANNIS application⁴ (see also Schmidt & Wörner 2014).

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Glossing

A morphological analysis by word classes and grammatical forms is a requirement for the following syntactical annotation. The glossing described here contains the word form as given in the text (on a diplomatic level with the expansion of abbreviations, including punctuation marks, however, ignoring special characters) in the tier **[text]**, its corresponding lemma in **[lem]** and the English translation in **[trans]**.⁵ The glossing itself is annotated in **[glos-morph]**. Following the above-mentioned projects in Germany, a variant based on the 'Leipzig Glossing Rules'⁶ was used for the declarations in the editor. Finally, the 'part of speech' is annotated in **[pos]**. In cases of subject and/or object drop (null-subject/object), *pro*-forms are inserted to the right of the finite verb (due to the right-peripheral inflectional morphology

¹ „Informationsstruktur in komplexen Sätzen – synchron und diachron“: http://dwee.eu/Rosemarie_Luehr/?Projekte_DFG-Projekte_Informationstruktur_in_komplexen_Saetzen_-_synchron_und_diachron; „Informationsstruktur in älteren indogermanischen Sprachen“: http://dwee.eu/Rosemarie_Luehr/?Projekte_DFG-Projekte_Informationstruktur_in_aelteren_indogermanischen_Sprachen. See also SFB 632 <https://www.sfb632.uni-potsdam.de/korpora.html>.

² <http://www.menota.org/menotec.xml>.

³ EXMARaLDA for Windows, tool-set 2017: <https://exmaralda.org/de/offizielle-version/>; <https://exmaralda.org/de/partitur-editor-de/>. The files are coded within an xml-format, which ensures that the data can be used rather flexible (easy data transformation with tools as Praat, ELAN, Transcriber etc.) and a long-living archiving. The files can additionally be transferred into various presentational formats (RTF, HTML, PDF) and can be converted for larger databases (e.g. PROIEL, ANNIS) using programs such as PAULA.

⁴ ANNotation of Information Structure: <https://corpus-tools.org/annis/>.

⁵ Within the corpus, all words get an English translation to make the annotation transparent for scholars not familiar with Old Norwegian. In addition, within the project "Syntactic Variation and Information Structure in Old Norwegian", a coherent translation of every sentence was inserted as an additional tier.

⁶ <https://www.eva.mpg.de/lingua/resources/glossing-rules.php>. The annotation in the corpus is reduced to: 1. Nouns (genus-case-numerus); 2. Adjectives, pronouns (genus-case-numerus); 3. Verbs (tense-modus-diatheese-person-numerus).

that Indo-European languages show). *Pro*-forms will usually be annotated to the right of the first finite verb even if they are copied within the same sentence. The same applies if there is more than one null-subject or null-object in a sentence, and if these refer to different entities. Thus, *pro* will be placed in the VP of the first finite verb that is influenced by the referential shift. Every null-element is marked with ‘#’ where it is important to do so (e.g. on the tiers **[text]**, **[v-sem]** (verbal-semantic)).

The glossing is done for all lexemes. Word-classes that do not have any inflection (prepositions, conjunctions, subjunctions, infinitive marker and interjections) do not get any annotation on **[glos/morph]**. Not included here are the so-called *semantic roles*.

[text]	- <i>diplomatic level (expansion of abbreviations); punctuation simply marked as <p>; pro-forms #</i>					
[lem]	- <i>lemma as is given in ONP-conventions⁷, pro-forms #</i>					
[glos/morph] (=glossing)	nouns (appellative and propria)	genus	numerus	case	degrees	definiteness
		M	SG	NOM		Ind
		F	PL	GEN		Def
		N	UNSPEC	DAT		
		C[ommune]		ACC		
		UNSPEC		OBL[ique] ⁸		
	adjectives (Haugen 2001:229-230)	in nominal use: +genus, +numerus, (attributive/predicative)		UNSPEC		pos
		in adverbial use: +grade			comp	
					sup	
	determinativa				UNSPEC	
	personal pronouns	-----			-----	
	interrogative pronouns/ indefinite pronouns				-----	
adverbials/particles	-----					
Pronouns are divided into three groups: 1) personal pronouns (word class is closed and includes <i>ek, vit, vér, þú, þit, þér, hann</i> and <i>hon</i> with 4/5 forms in SG, 2/5 forms in PL and 2 forms in DU); 2) interrogative pronouns (word class is closed and includes <i>hvat, hveim, hvílíkr</i>); and						

⁷ ONP: Dictionary of Old Norse Prose (<https://onp.ku.dk/onp/onp.php>).

⁸ When a form is syncretic and in non-nominative case (here: genitive, dative, accusative).

3) indefinite pronouns (word class is closed and includes *báðir*, *hvatki*, *hvatvetna/hvetvetna* and *manngi*).⁹

Additionally, there is a reflexive pronoun *sik* in the 3rd person (no nominative form, inflected in case) that is here accounted as a personal pronoun. Determinatives are *þat*, *þeir*, *þær*, *þau* (> *sá*) and can also function as personal pronouns in SG/PL. Determinatives are divided into the following groups¹⁰:

- 1) demonstratives (word class is closed and includes *hinn/inn/enn*, *sá* and *sjá þessi*);
- 2) quantores (word class is closed and includes *allr*, *annarr*, *annarrveggi*, *annarrveggja*, *báðir*, *einn*, *einnhverr*, *engi*, *fyrstr/fyrsti*, *hvárgi*, *hvárr*, *hvárrveggi*, *hvárrveggja*, *hvergi*, *hverr*, *nokkurr*, *samr* and *sumr*. In addition, there are cardinal numbers as well: *einn*, *tveir*, *þrír*, *fjórir*, *fimm*, etc.); and
- 3) possessives (word class is closed and includes *minn*, *þinn*, *sinn*, *okkarr*, *ykkarr*, *yðvarr* and *várr*).

Some words can be members of more than one word class.

For the verbs, only synthetic forms are annotated in **[glos-morph]** – periphrastic forms are annotated in **[grfunct]/[Comm]**. Historic present (PRS=PRT), too, is annotated separately with a mention in **[Comm]**.

	finiteness	tense	modus	diathesis	person	numerus
verbs (Haugen 2001: 222- 229)	fin[ite]	PRS (present)	IND[ikative]	ACT	1	SG
	inf[inite]	IPF (imperfekt=preterite)	IMP[erative]	MED (reflexive)	2	PL
	PRT (participle)*		OPT[ative]	UNSPEC	3	UNSPEC
			UNSPEC			

*plus annotation of tense (PRT=PF, PRT=PRS)

ON has two tense-forms: present and preterit

- present is an unmarked tense that can be defined as not-preterite (also used for the past : PRS=PRT *historic present*), atemporal relations (*maðr er manns gaman*) and the future tense)
- other tense-forms can be expressed by periphrastic forms : FUT: *munu+Inf*, PERIPHRAST.PF: *hafa+perf.part.* (in **[grfunct]/[Comm]**)
- aspect: the perfect does not have analytical forms. But there is a perfective content in *perf.part.* (*sleginn*, *kastaðr* with the verbs *vera* and *hafa*) – these are terminated actions.

⁹ See also Haugen & Øverland (2014) on pronouns in Old Norwegian.

¹⁰ See Haugen & Øverland (2014:32). Other grammars group possessives under the class of pronouns. This might be translated with the annotation value *prposs* instead of *detposs*. In these guidelines, both possibilities are presented in **[pos]**.

	<p>- The participle form or <i>supinum</i> (perf.part. and pres.part.) can be attributive, predicative or adverbial (nominalized) - pres.part. is no longer considered a verbal form; it is considered among adjectives (even though with some doubts)</p> <p>ON has <u>three modes</u>: indicative, optative and imperative</p> <p>➤ here the term <i>optative</i> is used : this is equivalent to conjunctive, however, the Germanic mode expressing possibility/wish is etymologically identical to optative, not conjunctive (see Ringe, 2017)</p> <p>ON has <u>three forms for diathesis</u> (voice of a verb ; describes the relationship between action and participants identified by its arguments; connected to semantic roles): active, mediopassive and passive, with own inflectional forms for active and mediopassive. The passive forms are often expressed periphrastical with <i>vera</i> or <i>verða</i> + perf.part. (in some cases reflexive forms may also have passive content) and are therefore not a part of the annotation mentioned above. In the Menotec-project the mediopassive forms are annotated as <i>reflexive</i>. For the project "Syntactic Variation and Information Structure in Old Norwegian" an annotation as mediopassive was kept.</p> <p><i>Examples:</i></p> <p>noun: hirðar: court(F):GEN.SG adjective: gamallar: old:GEN.F.SG.pos verb: skal: shall: PRS.IND.ACT.1SG</p> <p>complexe verbal forms: <i>em ... kominn</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="412 772 1424 949"> <tr> <td>text</td> <td>Ec</td> <td>em</td> <td>sva</td> <td>kominn</td> </tr> <tr> <td>lem</td> <td>ek</td> <td>vera</td> <td>svá</td> <td>koma</td> </tr> <tr> <td>glos/morph</td> <td>1.NOM.SG</td> <td>PRS.IND.ACT.1SG</td> <td></td> <td>PRT=PF.M.SG</td> </tr> <tr> <td>pos</td> <td>prpers</td> <td>vfin</td> <td>adv</td> <td>vadj</td> </tr> <tr> <td>grfunct</td> <td>subj</td> <td>prcompl-i</td> <td></td> <td>prcompl-i</td> </tr> </table>	text	Ec	em	sva	kominn	lem	ek	vera	svá	koma	glos/morph	1.NOM.SG	PRS.IND.ACT.1SG		PRT=PF.M.SG	pos	prpers	vfin	adv	vadj	grfunct	subj	prcompl-i		prcompl-i										
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<p>[pos] (=parts of speech)</p>	<p>- <i>separate between demonstratives (þat, sá > þ/s) and relatives (hverssu, osv. > hv/v)</i></p> <p>- <i>null-subjects/-objects are marked with #</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="412 1056 1986 1235"> <tr> <td>nouns</td> <td>noun</td> <td>noun.num</td> <td>noun.prt</td> <td>comp/adj</td> <td>comp/noun</td> <td>comp/adv (compound)</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>noun=vfin</td> <td>gerund (verbal noun)</td> <td>gerundive (verbal adjective)¹¹</td> <td>supinum</td> <td>vnominal</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>adjectives</td> <td>adj</td> <td>adj.compar</td> <td>adj.gerundiv</td> <td>adj.num</td> <td>adj.superlat</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>verbs</td> <td>vfin</td> <td>vinf</td> <td>comp/vfin</td> <td colspan="3">prt (participle; prt.prs.act ... prt.pf.med ...)</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>vadj</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	nouns	noun	noun.num	noun.prt	comp/adj	comp/noun	comp/adv (compound)		noun=vfin	gerund (verbal noun)	gerundive (verbal adjective) ¹¹	supinum	vnominal		adjectives	adj	adj.compar	adj.gerundiv	adj.num	adj.superlat		verbs	vfin	vinf	comp/vfin	prt (participle; prt.prs.act ... prt.pf.med ...)				vadj					
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¹¹ Gerundive: Especially in translations from Latin text; forms are similar to the pres.part. *Ekki er kristnum manni meir flýjanda en ofmetnaðr* from *Nihil magis Christiano vitandum est quam superbia*. This form is identical to the pres.part.; the difference lies in the semantics. Pres.part. is active and factual while the gerundive is passive and deontic. The gerundive in a typical construction is used as a predicative with the copula (*sjá kynning [...] er nemandi*).

	adverbs	adv	adv.compar	adv.cond	adv.correlat	adv.dir	advdem	advdem.correlat
		adv.num	advrel	advrel.correlat		adv.indef	adv.interrog	adv.superlat
	pronouns	prident	prindef	printerrog	prpers	papercraft (reflexive pronoun that is used as a personal pronoun)		
			prrefl	prposs				
	determinatives	detdem	detdem.correlat	detposs	detquan[tor]	detcard[inal]		
	others	part[icle] (also negation)		refl.part	conj[unction]	interject[ion]	subjunction	subjunction/rel
		inf.m[arker]		prep[osition]	postp[osition]			
	pro	pronoun deletion with simple verbs, after first finite main verb						
	<i>Example: auk næfni: comp/noun</i>							
[v-sem] (=verbal semantics)	desiderative	feeling	impersonal	knowledge	manipulative	modal	perception	
	performative	phasal	propositional	attitude	utterance			

There is a frequent group of words which can be members of more than one word class: e.g. *at* (preposition, subjunction, infinitive marker, adverbial, noun). Concrete relations of elements are annotated in the syntactic analysis in **[grfunc]**.

Saliency

This means semantic saliency (or animacy) which may be of importance for the position of topic or focus. Pronominal elements referring to salient elements are regarded here as well. Other types of saliency are annotated in e.g. **[givenness]** or **[definiteness]**. In accordance with the DFG-project, I use the *Animacy Hierarchy* (a variant of Silverstein 1976), where the status or degree of prominence of an entity is derived from its position within this hierarchy: Local person (= 1. und 2. Person) > Pronoun 3rd > Proper Noun 3rd > Human 3rd > Animate 3rd > Inanimate 3rd > Mass. The original hierarchy has been expanded with the category ‘proper noun’. Embedded clauses and infinitive clauses that are referred to, are handled like *abstracts*.

[saliency] (=semantic saliency)	nouns	nominal abstract denoting human	/animate
		animate	/collective
		inanimate	/unique (sól), concrete (can be touched), abstract
		human	/relative, collective
		proper	/animal, country, date, folk, human, lake, mountain, opus, place, plant, river
	pronouns	pr1	pr1.poss
		pr2	pr2.poss
		pr3	/deict, dem, refl, poss, interrog, indef, rel (/human, animate, inanimate) /refl

Saliency, givenness and definiteness can be seen as one unit. If one tier is given a value, all three tiers must be filled with an annotation.

Givenness, Definiteness, Context

These tiers cover the features of otherwise accessible information (*anchoring, bridging, part-whole, set-relation*) and its status (*new, given-active or given-inactive*). Following Götze et al. (2007) the information status can be divided into *given, accessible* (bridging, anchoring) and *new* information. These labels are annotated in **[givenness]**.¹² This may also interact with an element's status of definiteness. As grammatical definiteness is relevant to this research,¹³ it is annotated separately under **[definiteness]**. Just as it is the case in the tier **[saliency]**, *givenness* and *definiteness* are also annotated in cases of single pronouns referring to an element in the context. If a pronoun is found next to the noun it relates to and indicates its definiteness, this relation is shown by indices in both cells (noun and pronoun). Further information about its status of givenness and saliency will not appear in those cases, as the connection is clearly indicated, and further information can be drawn from the following cell (**[context]**). In **[context]** the kind of reference (anaphoric, cataphoric, deictic, situational etc.) that pronouns, particles, adverbials and nomina propria show, is annotated. The reference together with the above-mentioned categories is of importance for finding the position of the *topic*. The choice of the pronoun or determinative can influence the anaphor resolution (see *Givenness Hierarchy*).

[givenness]	- <i>link to [frame]; [giv]</i>		
	new giv (active) (giv) inact[ive]	access-gen[eral] access-sit[uational] anchoring bridging part-whole set-relation	(common ground – year, day etc.) (situational knowledge) (refers to given information, up-following features) (information that can be expected in the context) (subset, superset, part of the same set)
[definiteness]	- <i>pronouns/determinatives and a related noun are marked with the index def-i</i> def – indef – spec.indef (in case of numeral, f.ex. <i>þat sæm, noccora úvini</i>)		
[context]	pronouns/determinatives	ana.ref, kata.ref, deict.ref, demon/deict, demon/deict.ref, personal.deict, sit.deict	
	nouns	identity.ana, identity.ref	
	particles and adverbials	caus[al], comparative, concessive, conclusive, cond, connect, consecutive, contrast, contrastive/junctive, disjunct, fin, general[izing], iterative, junctive, junctive/corrective, junctive/neg, preterite, topic change	

¹² An information's givenness is a crucial feature for the ability of a discourse's element to be defined as the *topic*. If further pronouns refer to this element, decisions about its topic status are quite easily to be made, as personal pronouns (and anaphoric pronouns in general) often refer to *topics*, while demonstrative pronouns more often refer to non-*topics*. The more activated an element is in the addressee's mind, the minor the anaphoric degree will be.

¹³ Conclusions about an element's *topic* status can be drawn from its saliency, its givenness and its definite features.

	conjunctions	connect (combines two constituents), junctive (combines two sentences)	
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Frame

The theory of *schemes* and *frames* is dealing with the processing of entities that are in a firm relation to each other. Elements that a scheme contains can open a scheme by simply being mentioned. As soon as the scheme is active, other elements contained in the same scheme are treated like slots that want to be filled. If a slot is not saturated, the reader will fill it by inference (the typical information will be supposed).¹⁴ Though this information is not mentioned in the context before, its status can be neither *new* nor *given* but is a relation of its own: *bridging*. What effect this relation has, for instance, on an entity's possibility to be an utterance's *topic* is an important question (are there *frame-setting-topics*?, see e.g. Matic 2003; Reese et al. 2007 for a discussion). Frames can support new *topic*-candidates.

[frame]	- <i>main concept for topic (content)</i> scheme: X <i>Example: lýsi – scheme sun/light/warmth</i>
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Topic

In the annotation of immediate coherence between two sentences in **[topic]**, I follow Frascaralli & Hinterhölzl (2007) and their above-mentioned distinction into four types: 1) *continuing* (connected to previous information; carries on the topic of the preceding context), 2) *shifting* (the perspective changes to another referent; leads the discourse's perspective over to a new topic – not new information), 3) *familiar* (neither *smooth* nor *rough shift*, but shows the relation *continue* or *retain*; appears in pronominal or covert form and can therefore serve in both functions mentioned), and 4) *contrastive* (both what is talked about and utterance itself are emphasized; they limit the valid set for which the topic holds to a part of that set). Sentential as well as phrasal topic and focus positions (*initial*, *middle*, *final*, *preverbal*, etc.) are annotated in **[position-T]/[position-F]**.

[topic]	Con-T	Continuing topic						
	S-T	Shifting topic (perspective to a new referent)						
	C-T	Contrastive topic (or I-Topic, answers a question; stressed “also”)						
[position-F/-T] (=focus position)	- <i>multiple use possible</i>							
	initial	2P	post-2P	middle	final	all-focused clause	focus split	cov (with proforms)
	sub-initial	sub-2P	sub-post2P		sub-final	sub-all-focused clause		

¹⁴ This means that the mentioning of *apple* can open the scheme *tree*. Other elements of that scheme are the typical parts of the tree (*leaf*, *stem*, *branch* etc.) as well as its features like e.g. *to grow*, the *need of sun and water* etc. This scheme can be handled in different complexity in different contexts.

	/XP-initial			/XP-middle	/XP-final			
	/post/pre: -conj[unction] -demon -interrog -part -rel verbal							
	-compound sentence -parataxis -sub[ordinated structure]							

Comment/Focus

The comment-annotation is the domain that contains the focus. Focused information is not considered to be activated in the receiver's mind at the moment when the utterance is made. For that reason, there is no restriction on the word material that a *focus* can contain. Even single morphemes can be focused. However, note that also contrastive information can be focused, and the domain of contrast is given. First, the **comment domain** (which contains everything that can be focused/the widest possible *focus*) is annotated as *cm* in **[comment]**. The comment can be found alone (without a topic = all-focused sentence), while there must be a comment if a topic has been identified. The type of the *focus* (wide versus narrow *focus*) determines its further annotation. *New information focus* is annotated in **[NFocus]**, *contrastive focus* (as well as *verum focus* and *emphatic focus*) in **[CFocus]**.

[comment] (=focus domain)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - includes <i>New Information Focus, Contrastive Focus and non-focal elements</i> - <i>this is marked with cm</i> 	
[NFocus] (=new information focus)	Nf (new, normal focus) – nfsol (respond to a question)	
[CFocus] (=contrastive focus)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>note focus-particles, give indication of the position of C-Focus</i> - <i>contr: every element with new/own annotation</i> - <i>contrast paires: get indexation</i> - <i>(can include topic – contrastive topic: not to be annotated in the comment-domain)</i> 	
	contr (=Contrastive Focus)	contr-additive (“as well”) -neg/additive (“neither-nor”) -neg (“not; instead“) -scalar (“even”) -sel (“(either)-or”) -corr (“but“) -ident (“just”) -impl (f. ex. with comparatives/superlatives/intensifier)
	verum (=Verum Focus)	truth value of a sentence
	emph (=Emphatic Focus)	

Discourse, Style

The definition of discourse relations may be useful for the delimitation of elements relevant in the context of information structure. Those relations as well as speech acts are annotated in the tier **[discourse]** (e.g. explicit performance, directive etc.). The more content the following event description has in common with the previous one, the more clearly the narrative structure is shown. Additionally, the stylistic devices of classical rhetoric may have great influence on the sentence structure, as one can see in examples of prolepsis, hyperbaton, ellipsis, parallelism, chiasmus etc., but also other peculiarities as constructions of light-verbs. They are therefore annotated in **[style]**, following literary analyses.

[discourse]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>summarize: speaker + explanation</i> - <i>introduction/comment</i> 																																																														
	superordinate	introduction, commentary (personal opinion), direct speech, narration, reported speech																																																													
	subordinate	answer, background, commentator, consequence, continue speaker, contrast, correction, description, elaboration, explanation, introduction, narrative, narrator, precondition, question, quotation, request, result, source, stereotypical, expression, turn speaker1/speaker2/...																																																													
	<i>Example: direct speech/turn speaker2/answer</i>																																																														
[style]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>might be connected to [frame] (f. ex. comparison)</i> <table border="0" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td>accumulatio</td> <td>allegory</td> <td>alliteration</td> <td>anaphora</td> <td>anakoluthon</td> <td>antithesis</td> <td>antonym</td> </tr> <tr> <td>asyndeton</td> <td>chiasmus</td> <td>case form incongruent</td> <td>climax</td> <td>constructio ad sensum</td> <td>contractio</td> <td>idiomatic expression</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ellipsis</td> <td>epitheton</td> <td>figura etymologica</td> <td>formulaic expression</td> <td>hyperbaton</td> <td>inf.hist</td> <td>inversion</td> </tr> <tr> <td>impersonal construction</td> <td></td> <td>increasing terms</td> <td>indecl</td> <td>nominal clause</td> <td>onomatopoeia</td> <td>parallelism</td> </tr> <tr> <td>isocolon</td> <td>metaphora</td> <td>light verb construction</td> <td>personification</td> <td>polar expression</td> <td>polychronon</td> <td>polyptoton</td> </tr> <tr> <td>parenthesis</td> <td>pejorative</td> <td>repetition</td> <td>rhetorical question</td> <td>safigé</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>prolepsis</td> <td>rel.sentence</td> <td>tricolon</td> <td>zeugma</td> <td>...</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>similitude</td> <td>tmesis</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>							accumulatio	allegory	alliteration	anaphora	anakoluthon	antithesis	antonym	asyndeton	chiasmus	case form incongruent	climax	constructio ad sensum	contractio	idiomatic expression	ellipsis	epitheton	figura etymologica	formulaic expression	hyperbaton	inf.hist	inversion	impersonal construction		increasing terms	indecl	nominal clause	onomatopoeia	parallelism	isocolon	metaphora	light verb construction	personification	polar expression	polychronon	polyptoton	parenthesis	pejorative	repetition	rhetorical question	safigé			prolepsis	rel.sentence	tricolon	zeugma	...			similitude	tmesis					
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[orig]	- <i>original sentence (diplomatic level) with punctuation, copy of [text] for a better overview on a vertical level</i>																																																														
[transl]	- <i>translation to English, copy of [trans] for a better overview on a vertical level</i>																																																														

MC-layer and sublayers

The annotation done on these levels does not cover the entire sentence level but examines the layers that are distinguished into the *matrix clause* and (perhaps one or more) *sublayers*. The criteria for the different layer's tiers are the same for both matrix clause and subclauses (**ME- (matrix layer) and SE1- (sublayer), SE2-** etc.). Nevertheless, they have to undergo this separation, as e.g. an embedded clause may take the role of a sentence's subject or object. First in **[clause-st]** the domain of the matrix clause or the subordinated element is indicated. The clause status and type (declarative, exclamative, imperative, etc.) are also

mentioned here. It is important to know how an element is integrated or adjoined, since adjunction of embedded clauses may e.g. show different subject positions that are structurally important according to information-structural terms. In a next tier, **[grfunct]**, the function of the single elements is annotated. Note, however, that ‘single element’ does not mean a word-by-word annotation, since e.g. attributes can be linked directly to the unit they belong to without being defined themselves. This is annotated in order to make grammatical assignments of information structuring devices. Additionally, the semantics of adverbs and adjuncts are annotated. This is also relevant for determining the unmarked structure in *all-focussed* sentences. For periphrastic forms, the distinction between a non-finite lexical verb and finite verb (auxiliary or modal verb) is annotated in an additional tier **[aux]** by marking the finite verb form in these constructions with reference to the position relative to the non-finite lexical verb.

The number of syllables of a discourse unit (prosody) may have influence on the order in which various elements occur. The *heaviness* (Behaghel's *Gesetz der wachsenden Glieder*) is therefore annotated in **[syl_no]**. The position of central elements that indicate the sentence structure is accounted in **[word_order]** (verbal position as well as object position). The ME- and SE-layers have an additional translation tier in the mentioned project "Syntactic Variation and Information Structure in Old Norwegian" (German next to English) as some structures are better represented through a language with an active case system, and sentences with more than one embedded clause may be difficult to follow in the annotation. Thus, the reader may be better oriented within the context being provided with an additional translation. A further advantage of this extra-tier is the possibility to present an interpretation that is closer to the original text (in cases where such an interpretation would create confusion within the translation of the whole sentence).

[sentence_order] (ME/SE)	object-sentences	utterance/desiderative... obj/subj postverbal/preverbal/circumverbal/dislocated
	relative clauses and prt.conj.	rel/prt.conj circum-/pre-/postnominal/dilocated nucleus cov (if nucleus latent)
	adverbial subclauses	order is annotated f. ex. temp initial/pre loc; loc final/post mod
	generell	split/initial/middle/final/cov/post/pre-parataxis f. ex. caus initial
[clause-st](atus = sentence type) (ME/SE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>summary (including clause interpretation and position, f.ex. adv_clause, main/sub</i> - <i>parataxis: order of subordinated clauses</i> 	
	main	main:decl[arative]/excl[amative]/imper[ative]/inter[rogative]/(request: imper/inter)
	sub	sub:adversative/attr.mod/caus/comment/comparatio/concess/cond/contr/consecutive/fin/free relat/ generalizing rel/loc/mod/obj (object-sentences)/rel.non-restrict/rel.restrict/subj (subject-sentences)/temp /parataxis abl.abs/absolute.constr/ACI/ACP/apposition/attr.prt/gen.abs/inf.constr/locative.abs/NCI/

		prt.conj (participium conjunctum)/sentence equivalent (elliptic answer) relative_clause: dislocated or not rel/part.conj (position is given in relation)							
[grfunct] (=grammatical function) (ME/SE)	- <i>subject (subj) and predicate (pred/subj): same annotation on [pos]</i> - <i>prcompl: get indexation</i>								
		subj	exclam						
	objects	acc-o	comit-o	dat-o	dir-o (=retning)	gen-o	instr-o	loc-o	prep-o
	agens	dat-a	instr-a	prep-a					
		acc.resp (relational acc)		gen.partitivus	gen.comp	comp (comparative particle)			
	verbs	prsimpl		prcompl	v.nominal	v.copul (copula)			
	predicative expression	pred		pred/subj	pred/acc-o ...				
	appositions	app		app/subj	app/acc-o ...				
	attributes	attr		attr/subj	attr/pred	attr/adv:mod	attr/dat-o	attr/acc-o ...	
	adverbials	adv		adv:caus	adv:comit	adv:comp	adv:concess	adv:cond	
			adv:consecutive	adv:contr	adv:dir	adv:fin	adv:instr		
			adv:loc	adv:mod	adv:temp				
determiner	det		det/subj...						
other	interrogative marker		neg						
	NB : objects have to be required by a verbal choice between attr/dat-o or gen/dat-o > choose gen/dat-o to show case								
[aux] (=auxiliaries) (ME/SE)	auxF (position before the non-finite lexical verb) – auxL (position after the non-finite lexical verb)								
[syl_no] (= syllable-number) (ME/SE)	- <i>Phrases are summarized, combine columns or indexing -i</i> - <i>Phrases are: attributes + nucleus; subordinated sentences</i>								
[word-order] (ME/SE)	Verb position:								
	V1	V2	Vmiddle		Vend				

<p>/Vsplit /post-2P /pre-sub[ordinated structure] /post-sub /post-conj[unction] /post-adv /pre-parataxis...</p>																								
<p>enclitic cov (supplementary forms): for subjects that do not appear overtly</p>																								
<p><i>Object position:</i></p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>pre-</td> <td>post-</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">/V</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">/XV</td> </tr> </table>	pre-	post-	/V		/XV																			
pre-	post-																							
/V																								
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<p><i>Specifics in word order (derivates at the end):</i></p> <table> <tr> <td>AdvP-fronting</td> <td>AP-fronting</td> <td>DP-fronting</td> <td>PP-fronting</td> <td>incomplete VP-fronting</td> <td>left dislocation</td> </tr> <tr> <td>cleft</td> <td>pseudo-clefts</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>right dislocation</td> <td>right periphery</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>topic split</td> <td>true topicalization</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	AdvP-fronting	AP-fronting	DP-fronting	PP-fronting	incomplete VP-fronting	left dislocation	cleft	pseudo-clefts					right dislocation	right periphery					topic split	true topicalization				
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<p><i>Example:</i> V1/post-subj; V2/Vsplit – Vend/Vsplit</p>																								

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